

Error Analysis On Around-The-World Atomic Clocks Experiments⑨

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Abstract

This paper revisits the experimental paper from over 50 years ago, 'Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains', providing an in-depth analysis from the original concepts to the formula structure, while also proposing a self-derived formula 3 and comparing its $(\tau - \tau_0)$ values with those of the original formula in 'Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains'. The experiment 'Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains' did not achieve verification of relativistic time dilation, and even after 50 years, it is still not possible to verify time dilation. However, this paper adds a viewpoint: if the experiment were to provide real data, rather than emphasizing the high consistency between observed and predicted data as highlighted in the experimental paper, then this experiment would become a necessary and applicable engineering experiment.

Keywords

Uniform speed; time; Time dilation; Acceleration; Function; Independent variable; Dependent variable

In my article "Error Analysis On Around-The-World Atomic Clocks Experiments⑦"^{[2][3]}, there is the following passage: 'The screen display of all atomic clocks in the world can only show two types: one is the correct time reading, and the other can only be an incorrect time reading. The correct time reading is the result designed and produced by metrology experts, which is the oscillation of 9,192,631,770 cycles per second as defined by the International Bureau of Weights and Measures. An atomic clock can only run continuously at this frequency and cannot be changed, because this has already been limited by the definition of the International Bureau of Weights and Measures. The incorrect time reading occurs because the atomic clock has malfunctioned, or the environment in which it operates has a disturbing effect on the atomic clock. The incorrect time reading is due to a frequency shift generated by the atomic clock itself.' The above statement is clear and understandable. Looking back, there are more reasons to confirm the correctness of the above conclusion, and this article further explains the above conclusion.

My article presents formula 3 of my own design:

$$(\tau - \tau_0) = f(F, b, v, a, e, T, \dots) \quad \text{the self-made formula 3}$$

For the convenience of narration, $(\tau - \tau_0)$ here follows the formula writing style of the following two articles, and the titles of these two references^[4] are as follows:

1. Around- The- World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains Author(s): J.C.Hafele and Richard E.Keating Source: Science, New Series, Vol. 177, No.4044 (Jul.14,1972),pp.166-168
2. Around- The- World Atomic Clocks: Observed Relativistic Time Gains Author(s): J.C.Hafele and

Richard E. Keating Source: Science, New Series, Vol. 177, No.4044 (Jul.14,1972),pp.168-170

All four formulas from "Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains" are copied as follows:

$$\tau - \tau_0 = - (2R\Omega v + v^2) \tau_0 / 2c^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\tau - \tau_0 = [gh/c^2 - (2R\Omega v + v^2)/2c^2] \tau_0 \quad (2)$$

$$\tau - \tau_0 = 2\pi R/c^2 [gh / |v| - R\Omega v/|v| - v/2] \quad (3)$$

$$\tau - \tau_0 = \int [gh/c^2 - (2R\Omega v \cos\theta \cos\lambda + v^2)/2c^2] d\tau \quad (4)$$

The first Analysis:

The way the formulas are written in "Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains" is incorrect. The symbols on the left side of the four formulas are all equal, so these four formulas should all be equal. In fact, formulas (1) and (2), (3), (4) are not equal; formula (1) is only a part of formulas (2), (3), (4). This manner of writing causes confusion in the author's own expression. The writing of the above formulas suggests that although formula (1) can express speed as an independent variable in a separate equation, the frequency shift of atomic clocks caused by speed, even if it exists, cannot be displayed separately in $(\tau - \tau_0)$; $(\tau - \tau_0)$ can only represent the overall value of the atomic clock frequency shift. The value of time dilation cannot be extracted separately from $(\tau - \tau_0)$. This is the first question raised in this paper regarding the two papers of "Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains".

The second Analysis:

Please see formula 3 of my own design. In Homemade Formula 3, τ_0 is the time recorded by a standard ground clock for the plane to fly around the Earth once from take-off to landing. τ is the time recorded by the atomic clock on the plane for the plane to fly around the Earth once from take-off to landing. The original formula in 'Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains' does not label $\tau_1\tau_2\tau_3\tau_4$ separately because four caesium beam clocks participated in the experiment. Homemade Formula 3 only uses the simplified notation as in the original 'Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains'. In Homemade Formula 3, $(\tau - \tau_0)$ represents the difference between the total time taken by the plane to fly around the Earth and the total time recorded by the ground standard clock simultaneously. This difference was defined by the two scientists J.C. Hafele and Richard E. Keating as the value purely caused by relativistic time dilation effects. This is solely their subjective interpretation. $(\tau - \tau_0)$ represents the total frequency shift of the atomic clock during high-altitude flight affected by various factors and does not belong to any single factor alone.

In the formula 3 of my own design, the meaning of $(\tau - \tau_0)$ is the total scale display on the atomic clock of the frequency shift generated by the high-altitude flight, rather than the display of a single time dilation effect. The value of $(\tau - \tau_0)$ is the dependent variable of the multi-factor independent variables on the right-hand side. This paper analyses the relationship between the independent and dependent variables in homemade formula 3. In homemade formula 3, F represents the Earth's gravity experienced by the atomic clock; b represents the real-time magnetic field strength; v represents the uniform speed of the atomic clock, which is the uniform speed of the aircraft carrying the atomic clock; a represents acceleration. Einstein's time dilation effect does not include a horizontal acceleration term, but both horizontal acceleration and gravitational acceleration should affect the atomic clock. e represents changes in pressure; T , changes in temperature; and there may even be unknown factors, which we denote with ellipses. In short, this is a multi-factor issue. The above multi-factor functional relationship determines the frequency

shift generated when the atomic clock is in motion, and the total time scale value of the atomic clock frequency shift caused by all independent variables is $(\tau - \tau_0)$ in the homemade formula.

In the four formulas of American scientists, $\tau - \tau_0$ sometimes represents the theoretical predicted value, sometimes the measured value, sometimes merely the numerical value of time dilation due to speed, and sometimes the combined numerical value of time dilation due to speed and gravitational potential. The same letter $(\tau - \tau_0)$ has various different meanings, making the formula description very confusing. The experimental data collected by two scientists are claimed to have been processed with standard deviation, but the original data have not been published.

In the formula 3 of my own design, $(\tau - \tau_0)$ is the dependent variable of a composite function. We now need to consider separately the contributions of the independent variables F, b, v, a, e, T , etc. to the value of $(\tau - \tau_0)$. F represents the effect of gravity, which atomic clock experts can accurately answer. The effect of gravity should be determined by Newton's law of universal gravitation, which takes the form:

$$F = GMm / r^2$$

From Newton's law of universal gravitation, it can be seen that the distance r between the airplane and the ground is a variable, and this independent variable affects the value of the dependent variable $(\tau - \tau_0)$. b , magnetic field strength, the design of the atomic clock includes measures to shield against magnetic fields, this aspect requires assessment by atomic clock experts. v , the uniform motion term in the self-made formula 3, this term is a hypothetical independent variable because formulas (1), (2), (3), and (4) in 'Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains' all treat uniform speed v as the independent variable for $(\tau - \tau_0)$, so v is temporarily included in self-made formula 3 for analysis. My analysis is that the contribution of uniform speed v to $(\tau - \tau_0)$ is zero. This conclusion is the repeatedly proven view in 'Errors Revealed by the Global Atomic Clock Experiment ⑦'; this paper will provide some supplementary explanations, with speed v being analysed last among the independent variables.

a , acceleration a , its horizontal component's effect on $(\tau - \tau_0)$ is considered to truly exist in this paper, but this part is not included in relativity or in the experimental paper 'Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains'. During the aircraft's climb after take-off, the acceleration can be decomposed into horizontal acceleration and vertical upward acceleration. Expressed in formula:

$$a_x = a \cos \theta$$

$$a_y = a \sin \theta$$

Of course, this is only a simplified description. For a civil airliner, the climb angle θ can be considered constant, and the acceleration is regarded as uniform. The acceleration is formed by the resultant force and is given by the following formula:

$$\Sigma F_x = ma_x$$

$$\Sigma F_y = ma_y$$

The influence of acceleration on time dilation is far greater than that of velocity, a fact that can be judged by basic mechanical principles.

Acceleration exerts a force on an atomic clock, and as this force increases, its disruptive effects become evident. The force applied by acceleration to an object can be perceived by the object itself, which relates to the connection between force, deformation, and displacement. Similarly, humans can instinctively perceive the force exerted by acceleration. However, accurately measuring the magnitude of this force requires specialized instruments designed by experts; the

precise scale of the force cannot be naturally displayed by objects or the human body.

In summary, horizontal acceleration is a genuine independent variable that alters the value of $(\tau - \tau_0)$, and it should not be ignored merely because this variable was not accounted for in Einstein's time dilation effect.

When the airplane lands, the above acceleration components are opposite in direction to those during ascent, but their magnitudes are not equal due to the influence of gravitational acceleration. When the airplane rises, gravity does negative work. When the airplane lands, gravity does positive work, so the effect of acceleration on the atomic clock's rate will show a net value. I believe the functional expression for the time dilation effect of acceleration components in the x and y directions is unknown. What experimental method can be used to determine this functional expression? Determining this relationship will be very difficult because the experimental data for this is extremely hard to isolate and verify.

e: The Impact of External Pressure on Atomic Clocks

Analysis regarding the influence of external pressure on atomic clocks is omitted here, as atomic clock experts employ specialized designs to maintain constant pressure, and aircraft cabins are also equipped with pressure stabilization measures.

T: The Contribution of Temperature to the $(\tau - \tau_0)$ Value

The effect of temperature on $(\tau - \tau_0)$ of atomic clocks is evident. However, experts prioritize it as a key factor to prevent, ensuring that atomic clocks operate at a standardized temperature. Why can atomic clocks naturally sense temperature, leading to frequency shifts and directly altering the $(\tau - \tau_0)$ value?

Temperature perception is a natural phenomenon for atoms of all elements. Changes in temperature cause electron transitions, resulting in corresponding shifts in orbital energy levels and alterations in the internal energy of atoms. Consequently, the intrinsic frequency of cesium-133 atomic clocks changes, leading to anomalies in the displayed scale and deviation from the Bureau International des Poids et Mesures' definition of the second based on cesium-133 atomic clocks.

It is important to note that although atomic clocks can naturally sense temperature, they are not thermometers and cannot be used as such. They lack the design to display temperature scales. While materials in nature generally exhibit thermal expansion and contraction, we cannot rely on expanding/contracting railway tracks or mercury columns to indicate precise temperature values. The display of temperature scales is a specialized human design.

Returning to the discussion on the perception of uniform velocity v , atomic clocks lack the ability to perceive uniform velocity for several reasons.

All matter, objects, atomic clocks, and humans in nature lack the ability to perceive uniform velocity. This issue brings us back to the era of Galileo. In Galileo's thought experiment, inside the hull of a ship moving at a constant speed or at rest, with no external frame of reference for comparison, a person in the hull cannot perceive whether the ship is moving uniformly or is stationary. This demonstrates that humans inherently lack the ability to perceive uniform velocity. Unlike acceleration, uniform velocity does not exert a force on us or on atomic clocks, as uniform motion does not produce force-deformation effects. Even if uniform velocity has an effect on time dilation, it cannot be displayed in the atomic clock's $(\tau - \tau_0)$ value because atomic clocks are not specialized speed-measuring instruments. It is incorrect to interpret, as in the paper "Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains," formulas (1), (2), (3), and (4) by turning

uniform velocity into an independent variable of $(\tau - \tau_0)$. The two scientists imagined atomic clocks transforming from purely oscillation-based timekeeping instruments into speed-measuring devices. They further imagined that atomic clocks could perform calculations with independent variables in formulas and display the computed values on a screen. Even more problematically, they only allowed high-altitude, uniformly moving atomic clocks to display relativistic time dilation values in $(\tau - \tau_0)$, while prohibiting any errors from other frequency shifts.

The two scientists described in the original paper that the rate differences of atomic clocks in the laboratory could reach up to 1 microsecond per day. However, during high-altitude flights, these systematic rate (or frequency) differences, which were present in the laboratory, completely disappeared from the error values $(\tau - \tau_0)$ of the experimental atomic clocks. For clarity, The original text of the Around-The-World Atomic Clocks experiment is quoted as follows:

" However, no two "real" cesium beam clocks keep precisely the same time, even when located together in the laboratory, but generally show systematic rate (or frequency) differences which in extreme cases may amount to time differences as $1\mu\text{sec}$ per day. Because the relativistic time offsets expected in our experiments are only of the order of $0.1\mu\text{sec}$ per day (1,4) any such time divergences (or rate differences) must be taken into account. "

The second reason is that we humans did not equip atomic clocks with a speed measurement function. Unlike car speedometers, which can function as long as they are connected to the transmission, the speedometer on an atomic clock must be linked to the clock's intrinsic frequency, making it a major challenge in the universe.

The third reason is that atomic clocks need to be programmed with computational software so that they can recognise mathematical symbols and perform calculations. This analysis is sufficient; listing more is unnecessary.

In the article "Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains," the authors, Professors J.C. Hafele and Richard E. Keating, assume the atomic clocks have a speed measurement function. These professors not only assumed this function themselves but also led readers worldwide to assume the existence of this non-existent function.

To obtain the time dilation effect caused by speed from atomic clocks, first, the atomic clock must be able to sense speed, requiring the installation of a cosmic-level speedometer, as the principle of the speedometer on an aircraft is too simple and not compatible with the atomic clock; second, the atomic clock must distinguish different uniform speed scale values—can an atomic clock tell the difference between 800 and 1200 at uniform speed?; third, a logic operation program must be input, enabling the atomic clock to recognise and calculate the mathematical symbols in formulas (1), (2), (3), (4); fourth, the atomic clock must understand how to output the calculated data—should this output use the original atomic clock frequency, or a new frequency be designed? All these complex functions are still unavailable in any higher-precision atomic clock today. Regardless of how much the precision of modern atomic or optical clocks has improved, even the highest precision cannot compensate for a specific speed-detection function. In summary,

the various independent variables in the self-made formula 3 for $(\tau - \tau_0)$ contribute very differently; some have a genuine contribution, while others cannot contribute at all, especially the uniform speed term v , which cannot produce any contribution to $(\tau - \tau_0)$. Therefore, the uniform speed terms in the original formulas (1), (2), (3), (4) of "Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains" are meaningless for detecting time dilation, and $(\tau - \tau_0)$ does not include the scale values produced by uniform speed factors.

The third Analysis:

Another questioned issue is briefly discussed here, concerning equations (2), (3), and (4) in "Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains". In the aircraft's uniform cruise state, regarding the contribution of gravitational potential to the value of $(\tau - \tau_0)$, it has been mentioned that Newton's universal gravitation can affect atomic clocks in flight. However, regarding the effect of gravitational potential on the value of $(\tau - \tau_0)$, I present a different view and welcome criticism of any errors. A force analysis of the atomic clock during the aircraft's uniform flight stage is shown in Diagram 1:

1 Diagram The net force on the atomic clock is zero

From Figure 1, it can be seen that in the state of uniform horizontal flight of the aircraft, the net force on the atomic clock is zero. The gravitational potential energy of the atomic clock in the sky is conventionally described by mgh , but the atomic clock is fixed on an aircraft flying at a constant horizontal speed. In the reference frame of the aircraft, its h value is zero, so the gravitational potential energy mgh of the atomic clock on the aircraft is zero. Therefore, there is no effect of gravitational potential energy on the time scale of the atomic clock during uniform flight. If there is any impact, it is only due to the change in r in Newton's law of universal gravitation; as r increases, the gravitational force decreases. The gravitational potential energy mgh of the atomic clock on a uniformly flying aircraft relative to the ground is zero, because the atomic clock in the aircraft is supported by the aircraft, and gravitational acceleration does not exist. Its gravitational potential energy relative to the ground can only be zero.

In the vast expanse of space, there are countless celestial bodies, whose total mass is astonishingly large, and they are very, very far from our Earth. The mass of distant celestial bodies is immense, and the h value is infinite. According to the original formula in 'Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains', the combined gravitational potential energy mgh is unimaginably large; using 'infinite' seems far from sufficient. The infinite gravitational potential

energy of cosmic bodies could crush the Earth at any moment, which would certainly keep us awake at night. Those massive bodies do not pose any gravitational potential threat to the Earth when they are not in free fall towards it. Therefore, the gravitational potential energy term in the original 'Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains' should be removed from formulas (2), (3), and (4)! These formulas describe the uniform motion of the airplane, in which gravitational potential does not exist. If an atomic clock were to fall freely from the airplane, the conversion between potential and kinetic energy $mgh=mv^2/2$ could be used to calculate it. At that moment, the gravitational potential energy is meaningful for the atomic clock, which experiences gravity and gravitational acceleration, and the high speed caused by this acceleration could create a crater on Earth. In this situation, it is possible to attempt to detect the effect of gravitational potential energy on the atomic clock's time measurement.

Although this article believes that neither the constant velocity v nor the gravitational potential term gh/c^2 have a functional relationship with $(\tau - \tau_0)$, the Around-the-World Atomic Clock experiment still needs to be conducted. This experiment can help understand the comprehensive errors produced when atomic clocks operate at high altitudes, allowing metrologists to make justified corrections to the calibration values of atomic clocks.

From this perspective, the 'Around-the-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains' project should focus on practical research and abandon the illusory pursuit of explaining time dilation.

As long as this experiment is theoretically linked to relativity, it not only renders the experiment meaningless but also raises various questions about relativity.

Regarding the study of time dilation, I have discussions on Einstein's Lorentz transformation, in the Chinese-titled work 'Einstein Constructed the Special Theory of Relativity With Wrong Equations'^[5] (English title: 'The Relativity Theory is Fictional Theory')^[6].

I also have a dedicated article^[7] explaining that natural time and clock time have no functional relationship, and therefore any attempt to detect time dilation using clocks is illusory. If scientists cannot find a way to verify time dilation other than using clocks, it seems that time dilation can never be verified, and doubts about relativity will remain indefinitely.

Summary of the main conclusions of this article:

The predictions of the two time dilation values in equations (1), (2), (3), and (4) of the paper "Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains" do not appear in the atomic clock's $(\tau - \tau_0)$. The effect of horizontal acceleration on the time measurement of atomic clocks on an aircraft can be confirmed by classical mechanics, while the relativistic time dilation effect lacks such a description, but this does not affect the existence of this physical phenomenon. The time dilation effect caused by uniform motion in relativity is merely a theoretical speculation, and whether this theoretical prediction exists is still unknown. The major difficulty in testing this theory is that there are no available experimental instruments: speeds cannot be detected by all clocks, clocks are not designed for mathematical operations, and currently, there are no effective instruments available to verify time dilation. The relativistic time dilation effect could not be verified over 50 years ago and still cannot be verified even after more than 50 years. Regarding the general relativity gravitational potential effect mentioned in the original text of "Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains," this article analyses that the gravitational potential value for uniform flight of the aircraft is zero, and the gravitational potential assumed in the original text of "Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains" violates

basic rules of mechanics. Since the relativistic time dilation effect has not been confirmed by the "Around-The-World Atomic Clocks: Predicted Relativistic Time Gains" experiment, on the contrary, it has a significant negative impact on the theory of relativistic "four-dimensional space-time".

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[3] Link to this article: vixra.org/abs/2602.0138

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